

SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHING INTERNSHIPS: PROBLEMS, COPING STRATEGIES, AND TEACHING COMPETENCE

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the status of secondary teaching internships among student teachers in selected Local Colleges in Bohol during the School Year 2025–2026, focusing on problems encountered, coping strategies, and teaching competence. It aimed to determine how these variables relate to one another and to selected profile characteristics. A quantitative descriptive-correlational design was employed, using a modified and validated survey questionnaire administered to 220 respondents. Data were analyzed using percentage, weighted mean, Chi-square test, and Spearman rho. The findings revealed that problems encountered by student teachers were generally at a minor level, while coping strategies were utilized to a high to very high extent. Teaching competence was rated as very satisfactory, with classroom management as the strongest domain. Significant differences were observed in selected variables, particularly in relation to access to technological resources such as laptops. Correlation results showed that problems encountered were negatively related to both coping strategies and teaching competence, whereas coping strategies were positively associated with teaching competence. These results indicate that while challenges are inevitable during teaching internships, effective coping mechanisms play a critical role in maintaining and enhancing teaching performance. It is concluded that strengthening coping strategies and ensuring access to technological resources are essential in supporting the professional development and competence of student teachers.

Keywords: *secondary teaching internships, problems encountered, coping strategies, teaching competence, student teachers*

INTRODUCTION

Teaching internship is a vital component of teacher education because it allows student teachers to translate theoretical knowledge into actual classroom practice. Globally, internship programs serve as a bridge between pre-service preparation and the real demands of the teaching profession, helping future teachers develop confidence, professional identity, and teaching competence. Through classroom observation, lesson planning, instructional delivery, assessment, mentoring, and reflection, student teachers gradually learn how to manage learners, respond to classroom challenges, and apply appropriate teaching strategies.

In the Philippine context, teaching internships are guided by policies that ensure meaningful learning, student welfare, and safety during field practice. CHED Memorandum Order No. 104, series of 2017, emphasizes the importance of internship programs in providing students with quality exposure to real workplace settings. For teacher education students, this exposure is particularly important because the internship becomes their training ground for developing competence in lesson planning, classroom management, instructional delivery, and assessment practices.

However, teaching internship is not without difficulties. Student teachers often encounter personal-related problems such as physical fatigue, emotional stress, social adjustment, and financial constraints. They also face academic-related challenges involving technological, pedagogical, and content knowledge. These difficulties may affect their confidence, preparation, classroom performance, and overall teaching competence. In response, student teachers employ various coping strategies, such as seeking assistance from mentors, collaborating with peers, managing time, reflecting on their practice, and using available resources to overcome internship-related challenges.

Although several studies have examined teaching internships and the challenges experienced by student teachers, limited research has focused on the combined relationship among problems encountered, coping strategies, and teaching competence, particularly among secondary school student teachers in local colleges in Bohol. This gap is important because student teachers' internship experiences may vary depending on their personal circumstances, institutional support, available resources, and exposure to real classroom conditions.

Thus, this study aimed to determine the status of secondary school teaching internships by examining the problems encountered, coping strategies utilized, and teaching competence of secondary school student teachers in local colleges in Bohol during School Year 2025–2026. Specifically, it sought to describe the profile of student teachers, assess the level of personal and academic-related problems, determine their coping strategies, evaluate their teaching competence, and examine the differences and relationships among these variables. The findings served as the basis for proposing an action plan to improve internship implementation and support the development of competent, resilient, and professionally prepared future teachers.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the status of secondary teaching internships, the problems encountered, coping strategies, and teaching competence among secondary school student teachers in the Local Colleges in Bohol during the S. Y. 2025-2026.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of student teachers in terms of the following:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. gender;
 - 1.3. course; and
 - 1.4. gadgets and instructional materials used in teaching?
2. What is the level of the problems met by the student teachers in terms of:
 - 2.1 Personal aspect of
 - 2.1.1. physical;
 - 2.1.2. emotional;
 - 2.1.3. social; and
 - 2.1.4. financial?
 - 2.2 academic knowledge on:
 - 2.2.1. technological;
 - 2.2.2. pedagogical; and
 - 2.2.3. content?
3. What is the level of the coping strategies utilized by the student teachers for:
 - 3.1. personal-related problems; and
 - 3.2. academic-related problems?
4. What is the level of the teaching competence of student interns in terms of:
 - 4.1. lesson planning;
 - 4.2. classroom management;
 - 4.3. instructional delivery; and
 - 4.4. assessment practices?
5. Is there a significant difference between the profile and
 - 5.1. problems met;
 - 5.2. coping strategies; and
 - 5.3. teaching competence?
6. Is there a significant relationship between the level of student teachers' problems met, coping strategies, and the level of teaching competence?
7. What action plan may be proposed based on the findings?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed a quantitative descriptive-correlational research design to examine the problems encountered, coping strategies utilized, and teaching competence of secondary school student teachers. The descriptive approach was used to determine the profile of student teachers and the levels of internship-related problems, coping strategies, and teaching competence. The correlational approach was used to determine

the relationships among problems encountered, coping strategies, and teaching competence without manipulating any variable.

Research Environment

The study was conducted in selected local colleges in the Second Congressional District of Bohol, Philippines. These institutions included Buenavista Community College, Colegio de Getafe, Danao Technological College, Talibon Polytechnic College, and Trinidad Municipal College. They were selected because they offer Teacher Education Programs and implement teaching internship or practicum courses. The setting provided a relevant context for examining internship experiences in local higher education institutions.

Research Participants

The study involved student teachers enrolled in teaching internship during the second semester of School Year 2025–2026. The respondents were their cooperating teachers, mentors, and/or internship coordinators who supervised and evaluated the student teachers during their deployment in cooperating schools. The population included 508 student teachers and 220 cooperating teachers/mentors from the selected local colleges. Stratified random sampling was used to ensure proportional representation from each institution.

Distributions of Respondents

Name of Local College	No. of Student Teachers	No. of Cooperating Teachers/Mentors
Buenavista Community College	227	98
Colegio de Getafe	51	22
Danao Technological College	33	14
Talibon Polytechnic College	67	29
Trinidad Municipal College	130	57
Total	508	220

Research Instrument

Data were gathered using an adapted survey questionnaire composed of four parts. The first part gathered the profile of student teachers, including age, gender, specialization, and gadgets and instructional materials used in teaching. The second part measured the problems encountered by student teachers, adapted from Oquendo, Castro, and Zaragoza (2024), covering personal-related problems such as physical, emotional, social, and financial concerns, as well as academic-related problems involving technological, pedagogical, and content knowledge. Another part assessed coping strategies used during internship, while the final part measured teaching competence,

adapted from Lindeman, Schimmoeller, and Woods (2018), focusing on lesson planning, classroom management, instructional delivery, and assessment practices. The items were rated using a four-point Likert scale. Reliability was tested using Cronbach's alpha, with a target coefficient of at least 0.70.

Research Procedure

Before data collection, the researcher secured ethical clearance and permission from concerned authorities, including local college officials, research ethics committees, school administrators, and cooperating schools. Permission to use the adapted questionnaire was also obtained from the original source. During the pre-data gathering phase, the respondents were identified through stratified random sampling, and the instrument was prepared and pilot-tested among 30 cooperating teachers from Bohol Island State University–Calape Campus. During the actual data gathering, the researcher visited cooperating schools, oriented the mentors and coordinators about the instrument, and distributed printed questionnaires. The collected data were handled with confidentiality and used solely for the purpose of the study. After data collection, responses were encoded, organized, and validated for statistical analysis.

Data Analysis

Frequency and percentage were used to describe the profile of student teachers in terms of age, gender, specialization, and gadgets and instructional materials used in teaching. Weighted mean was used to determine the levels of problems encountered, coping strategies utilized, and teaching competence. The Chi-square test was used to determine significant differences in problems encountered, coping strategies, and teaching competence when grouped according to profile variables. Spearman's rho was employed to determine the significant relationships among problems encountered, coping strategies, and teaching competence. All statistical analyses were interpreted using the established four-point scales for level of problems, extent of coping strategies, and level of teaching competence.

For the Level of Problems Met by the Student Teachers, the following scale was used:

Scale	Range	Description	Interpretation
4	3.50 – 4.00	Always (A)	Very serious concern
3	2.50 – 3.49	Often (O)	Serious concern
2	1.50 – 2.49	Rarely (R)	Moderate concern
1	1.00 - 1.49	Never (N)	Not a concern

For the level of Coping Strategies, the following scale was used:

Scale	Range	Description	Interpretation
4	3.25 – 4.00	Always (A)	Very high extent
3	2.50 – 3.49	Often (O)	High extent
2	1.50 – 2.49	Rarely (R)	Low extent

1	1.00 -1.49	Never (N)	Very low extent
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For the Level of Teaching Competence, the following scale was used:

Scale	Range	Description	Interpretation
4	3.50 – 4.00	Proficient	Excellent performance
3	2.50 – 3.49	Adequate	Very Satisfactory performance
2	1.50 – 2.49	Developing	Satisfactory Performance
1	1.00 -1.49	Unsatisfactory	Poor Performance

RESULTS

This section presents the findings of the study, including the analysis and interpretation of the data gathered. It discusses the status of secondary teaching internships, the problems encountered, coping strategies employed, and the level of teaching competence among secondary interns in selected Local Colleges in Bohol during the School Year 2025–2026.

Table 1
Profile of the Respondents
n= 220

1.1 Age		Frequency	Percent	Rank
20	23	202	91.82	1
24	27	12	5.45	2
28	31	3	1.36	3
32	35	2	0.91	4
36	39	1	0.45	5
Total		220	100	
1.2 Gender				
Male		59	26.82	2
Female		161	73.18	1
Total		220	100	
1.3 Courses/Specialization				
BAEL		51	23.18	2
BTVTEd		14	6.36	3
English		141	64.09	1
Math		14	6.36	3
Total		220	100	
1.4 Gadgets/instructional materials				
Smartphone		115	17.27	3
Laptop		176	26.43	2
Tablet		11	1.65	7
Audio-Visual		63	9.46	5
PowerPoint		181	27.18	1
Tarp Papel		93	13.96	4
Others		27	4.05	6
Total		666	100	

Table 1 presents the profile of the student teachers in terms of age, gender, specialization, and instructional materials used in teaching.

In terms of age, the highest percentage of respondents belongs to the 20–23 age group (91.82%, Rank 1), followed by 24–27 years old (5.45%), while the lowest percentage is observed among those aged 36–39 (0.45%, Rank 5). This indicates that the respondents are predominantly young adults, which is expected in a tertiary education setting. The finding implies that the study largely reflects the perspectives of individuals in early adulthood—a developmental stage associated with identity formation, skill development, and career preparation. Thus, the experiences captured in this study are grounded in the formative phase of becoming future educators.

In terms of gender, the highest proportion of respondents are female (73.18%, Rank 1), while male respondents (26.82%, Rank 2) represent the lowest proportion. This shows that the teaching profession remains female-dominated. The implication of this finding suggests the need to encourage greater gender diversity in teacher education programs, as balanced representation may contribute to varied teaching approaches and improved student engagement.

In terms of course/specialization, the highest percentage of respondents are English majors (64.09%, Rank 1), followed by BAEL (23.18%), while the lowest percentage is shared by BVTED and Math (6.36%, Rank 3). This indicates a concentration of specialization in language education. The imbalance suggests that while there is strong preparation in English teaching, there may be a potential shortage of educators in other fields such as mathematics and technical-vocational education. This highlights the importance of aligning specialization offerings with broader educational needs.

In terms of instructional materials and gadgets, the highest usage is observed in PowerPoint (27.18%, Rank 1), followed closely by laptops (26.43%, Rank 2), while the lowest usage is noted in tablets (1.65%, Rank 7). The composite trend shows that digital tools dominate instructional practices among student teachers. This suggests that they are adapting to technology-integrated teaching; however, the low use of certain devices may indicate limitations in access or preference, pointing to the need for continuous support in digital resource utilization.

Overall, the findings show that the highest trends (age 20–23, female gender, English specialization, and PowerPoint usage) reflect a predominantly young, technology-oriented, and female-dominated group of student teachers. In contrast, the lowest trends (older age groups, male respondents, and tablet usage) indicate areas of underrepresentation. The composite interpretation suggests that while student teachers are aligned with contemporary educational practices, there remains a need to address imbalances in gender and specialization, as well as disparities in access to instructional tools. These findings are supported by Ingersoll and Tran (2023), who highlighted demographic patterns and workforce issues in teaching, and Tondeur et al. (2025), who emphasized the importance of preparing pre-service teachers for effective use of digital

technologies, reinforcing the need for balanced and well-supported teacher education programs.

Table 2.1
Level of the Problems Encountered by the Student Teachers in Terms of Personal Aspect
n=220

2.1.1. Physical As a mentor, I observed that the student teacher _____	WM	I
1. had difficulties in managing noise levels in the classroom, which can lead to physical strain on my vocal cords or hearing.	2.19	SC
2. experienced physical fatigue due to long hours of standing and constant movement in the classroom.	1.74	NC
3. encountered problems with organizing the classroom and managing resources, which resulted in physical discomfort due to the continuous bending, lifting, and carrying of materials.	1.81	MC
4. had difficulty giving personalized attention to each student, which led to physical exhaustion from continuously moving around the classroom.	1.85	MC
5. had trouble managing disruptive student behavior, which resulted in physical tension and stress.	1.95	MC
6. experienced physical discomfort due to inadequate classroom temperature or poor ventilation.	1.81	MC
7. faced physical strain from continuously bending to interact with students at their eye level.	1.67	NC
8. encountered difficulties in managing time and completing tasks, leading to physical stress and exhaustion.	1.90	MC
9. had difficulty maintaining and organizing the classroom environment, which resulted in physical discomfort and fatigue.	1.75	NC
10. faced physical strain from carrying heavy bags or materials for teaching, commuting, or attending professional development activities.	1.55	NC
Composite Mean	1.82	MC
2.1.2 Emotional		
As a mentor, I observed that the student teacher _____		
11. struggled with managing his/her emotions and maintaining a positive mindset in challenging situations.	1.86	MC
12. feel overwhelmed with balancing lesson planning, grading, and personal life.	2.24	MC
13. feel pressured to perform well and meet teacher's expectations.	2.16	MC
14. experience difficulty managing his/her emotions in front of the students whenever he/she get too angry.	1.83	MC
15. find it difficult to interact with parents, especially in challenging situations.	1.54	NC
16. experience setbacks or feel like the lesson didn't go well.	1.98	MC
17. doubt his/her teaching abilities.	1.99	MC
18. experience a hard time taking the constructive criticism and feedback from his/her cooperating teacher.	1.64	NC
19. find it hard to do his/her best at school because of the lack of support from his/her family.	1.41	NC
20. feel emotionally drained when trying to address the diverse needs of students, including those with learning disabilities or behavioral issues.	1.78	MC
Composite Mean	1.84	MC
2.1.3 Social		
As a mentor, I observed that the student teacher _____		
21. received lack sense of belonging and support from his/her colleagues.	1.50	MC

22. experienced being disrespected by the students.	1.80	MC
23. had lack of confidence in instructional methods, lesson planning, and adapting to unforeseen circumstances due to inexperience.	1.83	MC
24. experienced difficulty managing a classroom with diverse personalities, behaviors, and learning styles.	2.04	MC
25. experienced significant challenges when trying to communicate with students effectively.	2.04	MC
26. find it challenging to establish authority in the classroom, particularly when dealing with diverse groups of students.	2.08	MC
27. encountered difficulty in communicating effectively with parents and families of the students.	1.52	NC
28. struggled with building relationships and establishing rapport with students, especially when entering a new classroom or school environment.	1.75	NC
29. encountered difficulty in adapting to the social dynamics and expectations of different grade levels or age groups of students.	1.86	MC
30. experienced isolation or a sense of being an outsider, particularly when working in a new school or community where he/she had limited connections.	1.62	NC
Composite Mean	1.80	MC
2.1.4 Financial		
As a mentor, I observed that the student teacher _____		
31. don't have enough money to buy the necessary materials for the lesson (s).	1.95	MC
32. experience paying a big amount for the high transportation fare.	1.86	MC
33. finds it hard to allocate the money given by his/her family/guardian.	1.92	MC
34. don't have enough allowance for everyday expenses because of financial instability.	1.94	MC
35. feel beaten down by money worries due to the high prices of products.	1.98	MC
36. struggle to create a financial plan due to the unexpected expenses.	1.98	MC
37. experience difficulty in applying financial literacy.	1.86	MC
38. compulsively buy unnecessary products, leading to his/her insufficient allowance.	1.68	MC
39. experience a lack of funding to buy needed gadgets for the teaching process.	1.96	MC
40. experience difficulty in his/her money matters due to personal needs.	1.86	MC
Composite Mean	1.90	MC
Overall Composite Mean	1.84	MC

Legend:

- 1.00 – 1.49 Not a Concern (NC)
- 1.50 – 2.49 Minor Concern (MC)
- 2.50 – 3.49 Serious Concern (SC)
- 3.50 - 4.00 Very Serious Concern (VSC)

Table 2.1 presents the levels of problems encountered by student teachers in terms of physical, emotional, social, and financial aspects.

In terms of physical problems, the highest weighted mean is observed in the item *“had difficulties in managing noise levels in the classroom...”* with a mean of 2.19 (MC), indicating that classroom noise contributes to physical strain such as vocal fatigue and stress. Meanwhile, the lowest mean is recorded in *“faced physical strain from carrying heavy bags or materials”* with 1.55 (NC). The composite mean of 1.82 (MC) indicates that physical concerns are generally minor but present among student teachers. This suggests that while physical strain exists, it is not severe but still affects teaching performance, particularly in classroom management situations.

In terms of emotional problems, the highest mean is “*feel overwhelmed with balancing lesson planning, grading, and personal life*” with 2.24 (MC), while the lowest mean is “*lack of support from family*” with 1.41 (NC). The composite mean of 1.84 (MC) indicates that emotional challenges are also minor concerns. This implies that workload-related stress is a more significant emotional issue than external family support, highlighting the pressure associated with instructional responsibilities.

For social problems, the highest mean is “*challenging to establish authority in the classroom*” with 2.08 (MC), whereas the lowest mean is “*lack of sense of belonging and support from colleagues*” with 1.50 (MC). The composite mean of 1.80 (MC) shows that social concerns are the lowest among all areas, though still categorized as minor. This indicates that while student teachers face challenges in classroom authority and communication, they generally manage social interactions within the school environment.

In terms of financial problems, the highest means are observed in “*feel beaten down by money worries due to high prices of products*” and “*struggle to create a financial plan due to unexpected expenses*”, both with 1.98 (MC). The lowest mean is “*compulsively buying unnecessary products*” with 1.68 (MC). The composite mean of 1.90 (MC) indicates that financial concerns are the highest among all aspects, although still within the “minor concern” range. This suggests that student teachers experience financial pressure, particularly related to daily expenses and budgeting, which may affect their overall well-being. Overall, the highest composite mean is found in the financial aspect (1.90, MC), while the lowest composite mean is in the social aspect (1.80, MC). The overall composite mean of 1.84 (MC) indicates that student teachers experience minor concerns across all domains. This means that although challenges exist in physical, emotional, social, and financial areas, these do not severely hinder their performance and remain manageable.

These findings are supported by recent studies. Kim (2024) found that stress and coping demands contribute to physical strain and fatigue among students, aligning with the observed physical challenges. Similarly, Pineda et al. (2024) emphasized that balancing instructional tasks and personal life leads to emotional stress among pre-service teachers. Furthermore, Iqbal and Ali (2024) highlighted difficulties in establishing classroom authority among student teachers, supporting the social findings. Lastly, Nasr et al. (2024) confirmed that financial stress remains a common concern among students and pre-service teachers.

Table 2.2
Level of the Problems Encountered by the Student Teachers in Terms of Academic Knowledge
n=220

2.2.1 Technological Knowledge As a mentor, I observed that the student teacher _____	WM	I
1. difficulty in operating modernized technology due to a lack of knowledge.	1.86	MC
2. challenge in using technology in delivering the lesson.	1.88	MC

3. struggle in balancing the usage of traditional and modernized technology for the instructional materials.	1.84	MC
4. hard time integrating appropriate technology in the teaching process.	1.81	MC
5. unfamiliarity with the applications used for better lesson presentation.	1.86	MC
6. difficulty in making modernized instructional materials because he/she don't have the necessary gadgets to be used.	1.83	MC
7. challenge in navigating lesson resources from social media platforms.	1.83	MC
8. issues in using/navigating advanced technologies provided by the DepEd.	1.79	MC
9. complications in creating assessments using modern technologies.	1.88	MC
10. hard time in creating modern presentations that address different learning styles of students using technologies.	1.95	MC
Composite Mean	1.85	MC
2.2.2 Pedagogical		
As a mentor, I observed tha the student teacher _____		
11. difficulty in implementing different teaching strategies that are responsive to the different learning styles of learners.	2.18	MC
12. hardship in classroom management in the teaching and learning process.	2.10	MC
13. hard time in discussing the lesson using different languages and a range of strategies for communicating learner needs, progress and achievement.	2.06	MC
14. limitation in applying theories I learned into the real field of teaching.	2.12	MC
15. struggle in formulating different assessment techniques that are adaptive to the diversity of learners.	2.15	MC
16. obstacle in relating the new lessons to the past ones.	2.00	MC
17. hard time in manipulating and using tools needed for the teaching process.	1.98	MC
18. struggle in formulating examples that are relevant to the real-world scenarios.	2.06	MC
19. difficulty in constructing questions that addresses higher order skills.	2.12	MC
20. struggle in maintaining interaction in the teaching and learning process.	2.00	MC
Composite Mean	2.08	MC
2.2.3. Content		
As a mentor, I observed tha the student teacher _____		
21. have hard time in demonstrating content knowledge and its application within and/or across curriculum teaching areas.	2.23	MC
22. lacks knowledge of the lessons they need to teach to students.	1.94	MC
23. struggle to implement educational philosophies in the teaching and learning process.	2.12	MC
24. have issues mastering theories applicable in the classroom.	2.13	MC
25. struggle in making SMART objectives for the lessons.	2.10	MC
26. experience difficulty in making lesson plans aligned to the Curriculum.	2.03	MC
27. have a hard time formulating a comprehensive explanation regarding the content of the subject matter.	2.11	MC
28. face hardship in understanding the curriculum.	2.07	MC
29. struggle in creating content-relevant assessments.	2.04	MC

30. struggle in internalizing the concepts that he/she will teach to the students.	2.05	MC
Composite Mean	2.08	MC
Overall Composite Mean	2.00	MC

Legend:

- 1.00 – 1.49 Not a Concern (NC)
- 1.50 – 2.49 Minor Concern (MC)
- 2.50 – 3.49 Serious Concern (SC)
- 3.50 - 4.00 Very Serious Concern (VSC)

Table 2.2 presents the level of problems encountered by student teachers in terms of academic knowledge, specifically in technological, pedagogical, and content domains.

In terms of technological knowledge, the highest weighted mean is observed in *“hard time in creating modern presentations that address different learning styles of students using technologies”* with 1.95 (MC). This indicates that adapting technology to diverse learners remains a challenge. On the other hand, the lowest mean is *“issues in using/navigating advanced technologies provided by the DepEd”* with 1.79 (MC). The composite mean of 1.85 (MC) suggests that technological concerns are generally minor and manageable. This implies that while student teachers are capable of using technology, they still encounter difficulties in maximizing its potential for differentiated instruction and presentation.

For pedagogical knowledge, the highest mean is *“difficulty in implementing different teaching strategies responsive to learners’ styles”* with 2.18 (MC), while the lowest mean is *“hard time in manipulating and using tools needed for the teaching process”* with 1.98 (MC). The composite mean of 2.08 (MC) indicates that pedagogical concerns are relatively higher compared to technological aspects. This implies that student teachers struggle more with applying appropriate teaching strategies and adapting instruction to diverse learners, highlighting the complexity of actual classroom practice.

In terms of content knowledge, the highest mean is *“hard time in demonstrating content knowledge and its application across curriculum areas”* with 2.23 (MC), while the lowest mean is *“lacks knowledge of the lessons to be taught”* with 1.94 (MC). The composite mean of 2.08 (MC) shows that content-related challenges are also relatively high, similar to pedagogical concerns. This suggests that while student teachers possess basic knowledge, they experience difficulty in applying, integrating, and explaining content effectively across different contexts.

Overall, the highest composite means are found in both pedagogical and content domains (2.08, MC), while the lowest composite mean is in the technological domain (1.85, MC). The overall composite mean of 2.00 (MC) indicates that student teachers experience minor concerns across all academic knowledge areas, though pedagogical and content aspects require more attention. This implies that while technological readiness is evident, greater support is needed in strengthening teaching strategies and

deepening subject mastery. These findings are supported by recent studies. Widiastutik et al. (2025) and Lu et al. (2025) emphasized that student teachers face challenges in effectively integrating technology into instruction despite its availability. Similarly, Masood et al. (2022) highlighted difficulties in implementing diverse instructional strategies for varied learners, while Chavira-Quintero and Olais-Govea (2023) noted weak integration of content and pedagogy in teaching practice.

Table 3.1
Level of Coping Strategies Utilized by Student Teachers for Personal-related Problems
n=220

3.1.1 Physical As a mentor, I observed that the student teacher _____	WM	I
1. confront the student making noise in the class calmly.	3.04	HE
2. take sometime to sit down during and after the discussions.	2.51	HE
3. usually use handy and lightweight materials for the teaching and learning process.	3.11	HE
4. louder his/her voice during the lesson to engage everybody in the class without too much moving around.	3.30	VHE
5. talk with the students regarding the reason why they are doing such actions and behaviors.	2.96	HE
6. use fan and bring an extra t-shirt that will ease the hotness of the surroundings.	2.10	LE
7. practice eye contact to the students without bending and kneeling to be at their eye level.	3.17	HE
8. create a schedule and practice time-management techniques.	3.17	HE
9. ask help from his/her students in organizing the room and also implement classroom rules to maintain classroom cleanliness.	3.14	HE
10. utilize lightweight backpacks or bags with proper support.	3.19	HE
Composite Mean	2.97	HE
3.1.2 Emotional As a mentor, I observed that the student teacher _____		
11. asked for advice regarding any challenges from the cooperating teacher.	3.34	VHE
12. prioritize tasks, create a realistic schedule, and learn to say no to additional commitments.	3.15	HE
13. lower his/her expectations and do my tasks one at a time.	3.19	HE
14. control his/her emotions after he/she gets angry in front of my students.	3.40	VHE
15. seek guidance from the cooperating teacher on handling challenging interactions.	3.47	VHE
16. ask his/her students questions about the lessons.	3.48	VHE
17. just keep moving forward, and he/she lowers his/her expectations.	3.21	HE
18. ask his/her cooperating teacher what he/she should do next to improve.	3.39	VHE
19. seek support from his/her friends and other family members.	3.21	HE
20. cultivate empathy for the students, communicate, and seek advice from the cooperating teacher.	3.32	VHE
Composite Mean	3.32	VHE
3.1.3 Social		

As a mentor, I observed that the student teacher _____		
21. make an effort to meet new people. He/she recognizes and addresses negative thoughts and beliefs that may be contributing to the feeling of being out of place.	3.29	VHE
22. remain calm, he/she take deep breath and allows the students to express themselves and be heard.	3.47	VHE
23. focus on his/her strengths, and he/she acknowledges his/her unique qualities and talents.	3.48	VHE
24. build a good relationship with the students and show genuine interest in their lives.	3.58	VHE
25. use clear and concise language to ensure good communication with the students.	3.44	VHE
26. address any behavior issues promptly and directly in a calm and controlled manner.	3.42	VHE
27. use multiple communication channels, such as email and phone calls, to reach out to students' parents and families.	2.85	HE
28. showed empathy and understanding to the students by acknowledging their feelings and perspectives.	3.46	VHE
29. reached out to experienced teachers or mentors who have worked with similar grade levels or age groups.	3.29	VHE
30. often communicated with the various stakeholders of the school.	2.84	HE
Composite Mean	3.31	VHE
3.1.4 Financial		
As a mentor, I observed that the student teacher _____		
31. create a monthly budget to take control of your finances and avoid overspending.	2.81	HE
32. always choose to ride on the cheapest public transportation.	3.27	VHE
33. reach out to his/her family and to his/her fellow pre-service teacher for coping with financial stress.	2.97	HE
34. take control of managing his/her own money and impose discipline on himself/herself regarding spending.	3.34	VHE
35. make adjustments in his/her budget and lifestyle if needed.	3.40	VHE
36. save his/her own money to help him/her build a stable financial future.	3.30	VHE
37. take time to learn financial literacy knowledge and try to practice it.	3.19	HE
38. plan regarding the things he/she's buying to prevent allowance insufficiency.	3.26	VHE
39. use recyclable or cheap materials for the lessons if possible.	3.16	HE
40. experience difficulty in his/her money matters due to personal needs.	2.82	HE
Composite Mean	3.15	HE
Overall Weighted Mean	3.19	HE

Legend:

- 1.00 – 1.49 Very Low Extent (VLE)
- 1.50 – 2.49 Low Extent (LE)
- 2.50 – 3.49 High Extent (HE)
- 3.50 - 4.00 Very High Extent (VHE)

Table 3.1 presents the level of coping strategies utilized by student teachers in addressing personal-related problems across physical, emotional, social, and financial domains.

In terms of the physical domain, the highest weighted mean is observed in *“louder his/her voice during the lesson to engage everybody in the class without too much moving around”* with 3.30 (VHE), indicating that student teachers strongly rely on voice modulation as a strategy to manage classroom engagement while minimizing physical strain. On the other hand, the lowest mean is *“use a fan and bring an extra t-shirt...”* with 2.10 (LE). The composite mean of 2.97 (HE) suggests that physical coping strategies are utilized to a high extent. This implies that while student teachers actively apply strategies to manage physical demands, simpler comfort-based approaches are less practiced.

For the emotional domain, the highest mean is *“ask questions to students about the lessons”* with 3.48 (VHE), closely followed by other strategies involving seeking guidance and emotional regulation. The lowest mean is *“prioritize tasks, create a realistic schedule, and learn to say no”* with 3.15 (HE). The composite mean of 3.32 (VHE) indicates that emotional coping strategies are practiced to a very high extent, making it the highest among all domains. This suggests that student teachers demonstrate strong emotional resilience by seeking support, regulating emotions, and maintaining positive interactions in the classroom.

In terms of the social domain, the highest mean is *“build a good relationship with the students and show genuine interest in their lives”* with 3.58 (VHE), while the lowest mean is *“often communicated with different stakeholders of the school”* with 2.84 (HE). The composite mean of 3.31 (VHE) indicates that social coping strategies are also utilized to a very high extent. This implies that student teachers prioritize building rapport with students; however, communication with broader stakeholders such as parents and administrators is comparatively less emphasized.

For the financial domain, the highest mean is *“make adjustments in budget and lifestyle if needed”* with 3.40 (VHE), while the lowest mean is *“create a monthly budget...”* with 2.81 (HE). The composite mean of 3.15 (HE) indicates that financial coping strategies are utilized to a high extent. This suggests that while student teachers adjust their spending and lifestyle in response to financial challenges, structured financial planning strategies are less consistently practiced.

Overall, the highest composite mean is observed in the emotional domain (3.32, VHE), while the lowest composite mean is in the physical domain (2.97, HE). The overall weighted mean of 3.19 (HE) indicates that student teachers utilize coping strategies to a high extent across all domains. This implies that despite experiencing various challenges, student teachers actively employ effective coping mechanisms, particularly in managing emotional and social demands, while physical coping strategies require further strengthening. These findings are supported by recent studies. Krisdianata and Mbato (2022) highlighted that student teachers demonstrate resilience through emotional regulation and support-seeking behaviors during practicum experiences. Similarly,

Hagenauer et al. (2024) emphasized the importance of building positive relationships with students as a key coping and engagement strategy. Furthermore, Oduro (2026) underscored the role of continuous support systems in enhancing teacher competencies, reinforcing the importance of structured coping mechanisms.

Table 3.2
Level of Coping Strategies Utilized by Student Teachers for Academic-related Problems
n=220

3.2.1. Technological As a mentor, I observed that the student teacher _____	WM	I
1. follow the step-by-step procedure of how to use modernized technology.	3.38	VHE
2. seek guidance from the mentors about the proper way to use technology in delivering lessons.	3.34	VHE
3. plan regarding what appropriate instructional materials he/she will use beforehand.	3.44	VHE
4. consult guidance on experienced teachers who can provide valuable insights and guidance on integrating technology into the classroom.	3.34	VHE
5. watch instructional videos about creating innovative presentations of lessons.	3.34	VHE
6. borrow gadgets from his/her friends, classmates, or relatives.	2.88	HE
7. evaluate online resources thoroughly.	3.21	HE
8. take time in learning the manuals on how to use the technologies provided by the DepEd.	3.14	HE
9. read different resources regarding the procedure for creating assessments.	3.28	VHE
10. create presentations that appeal to the different senses.	3.38	VHE
Composite Mean	3.27	VHE
3.2.2 Pedagogical As a mentor, I observed that the student teacher _____	WM	I
11. plan his/her instruction and group students flexibly to help them address their individual strengths and needs.	3.36	VHE
12. implement class rules in the classroom.	3.65	VHE
13. practice using appropriate languages for his/her lesson.	3.47	VHE
14. seek guidance from mentors, and he/she continuously practice to master the art of teaching.	3.50	VHE
15. attend seminars and workshops that help him/her in different assessment techniques for the students.	2.80	HE
16. make sure that there is a review of the previous lesson to be able to connect the new lesson.	3.53	VHE
17. practice in using needed tools in the teaching process.	3.43	VHE
18. plan regarding the examples that he/she will share with the students.	3.42	VHE
19. seek guidance from his/her former teachers.	3.24	HE
20. use activities that are engaging to maintain interaction in the class.	3.40	VHE
Composite Mean	3.38	VHE
3.2.3 Content As a mentor, I observed that the student teacher _____		
21. spend some time revisiting the curriculum, so he/she can teach it smoothly and thoroughly.	3.12	VHE

22. take time for self-learning and make use of textbooks, online resources, and educational videos to improve his/her grasp of the topic.	3.38	VHE
23. reach out to knowledgeable mentors who can share practical tips on integrating these philosophies.	3.35	VHE
24. review the theories that can support and improve his/her teaching and learning process.	3.29	VHE
25. use the SMART approach when writing lesson objectives.	3.42	VHE
26. prepare his/her lesson plan carefully and ensure it aligns with the curriculum.	3.47	VHE
27. watch instructional videos to gain additional insights and knowledge.	3.38	VHE
28. connect with his/her colleagues to share insights and learn from one another	3.45	VHE
29. read useful materials to improve my skills in creating assessments.	3.43	VHE
30. go through relevant resources to strengthen his/her knowledge of the topics.	3.43	VHE
Composite Mean	3.38	VHE
Overall Composite Mean	3.34	HE

Legend:

- 1.00 – 1.49 Very Low Extent (VLE)
- 1.50 – 2.49 Low Extent (LE)
- 2.50 – 3.49 High Extent (HE)
- 3.50 - 4.00 Very High Extent (VHE)

Table 3.2 presents the level of coping strategies utilized by student teachers in addressing academic-related problems across technological, pedagogical, and content knowledge domains.

In terms of technological coping strategies, the highest weighted mean is “*plan regarding what appropriate instructional materials he/she will use beforehand*” with 3.44 (VHE), indicating that proactive planning is a key strategy in managing technological challenges. Meanwhile, the lowest mean is “*borrow gadgets from friends, classmates, or relatives*” with 2.88 (HE). The composite mean of 3.27 (VHE) shows that student teachers utilize technological coping strategies to a very high extent. This implies that while they actively plan and seek guidance in using technology, reliance on borrowed devices is less preferred and less sustainable as a coping mechanism.

For pedagogical coping strategies, the highest mean is “*implement class rules in the classroom*” with 3.65 (VHE), while the lowest mean is “*attend seminars and workshops...*” with 2.80 (HE). The composite mean of 3.38 (VHE) indicates that pedagogical coping strategies are practiced to a very high extent, making it one of the highest domains. This suggests that student teachers strongly rely on classroom management practices and continuous mentoring, although participation in formal professional development activities is relatively less emphasized.

In terms of content coping strategies, the highest mean is “*prepare lesson plan carefully and ensure alignment with the curriculum*” with 3.47 (VHE), while the lowest mean is “*spend time revisiting the curriculum...*” with 3.12 (VHE). The composite mean

of 3.38 (VHE) indicates that content-related coping strategies are also utilized to a very high extent, similar to pedagogical strategies. This implies that student teachers prioritize lesson planning, resource utilization, and collaboration to strengthen their subject mastery and instructional delivery.

Overall, the highest composite means are found in both pedagogical and content domains (3.38, VHE), while the lowest composite mean is in the technological domain (3.27, VHE). The overall composite mean of 3.34 (HE) indicates that student teachers utilize coping strategies to a high to very high extent across all academic domains. This implies that although they encounter minor academic-related problems, they are highly proactive, organized, and capable of addressing these challenges effectively, particularly in pedagogy and content mastery. These findings are supported by recent studies. Hojeij et al. (2023) emphasized that strong mentorship and classroom management practices enhance student teachers' pedagogical coping abilities. Similarly, Beckmann and Ehmke (2023) found that lesson planning competence significantly improves during teaching internships, aligning with the high use of content-related strategies. Furthermore, Ghufuron et al. (2022) highlighted that reflective practice and continuous teaching experience strengthen coping strategies among pre-service teachers.

Table 4
Level of the Teaching Competence of Student Teachers
n=220

4.1 Lesson Planning As a mentor, I observed that the student teacher __	WM	I
1. used student learning data to guide planning	3.31	VSP
2. planned time realistically for pacing, content mastery, and transitions.	3.37	VSP
3. aligned instructional objectives to the school's pacing guide, program of studies.	3.43	VSP
4. planned for differentiation	3.26	VSP
Composite Mean	3.34	VSP
4.2 Classroom Management As a mentor, I observed that the student teacher __		
5. arranged the classroom to maximize learning while providing a safe environment and established clear expectations for classroom rules and procedures.	3.45	VSP
6. promoted culture sensitivity by respecting students' diversity, including language, culture, race, gender, and special needs	3.44	VSP
7. maximized instructional time and minimized disruptions.	3.42	VSP
8. established a climate of trust and teamwork by being fair, caring, respectful and enthusiastic.	3.52	EP
Composite Mean	3.46	EP
4.3 Instructional Delivery		
9. engaged and maintains students in active learning.	3.47	VSP
10. differentiated instruction to meet the students' needs.	3.30	VSP
11. used a variety of effective instruction strategies and resources.	3.41	VSP
12. communicated clearly and checked for understanding.	3.46	VSP
Composite Mean	3.41	VSP

4.4 Assessment Practice		
As a mentor, I observed that the student teacher __		
13.communicated expectations with clarity.	3.48	VSP
14.involved students in setting learning goals and monitoring their own progress.	3.45	VSP
15.aligned student assessment with established curriculum standards and benchmarks.	3.47	VSP
16.gave constructive and frequent feedback to students on their learning.	3.40	VSP
Composite Mean	3.45	VSP
Overall Composite Mean	3.42	VSP

Legend:

- 1.00 – 1.49 Poor Performance (PP)
- 1.50 – 2.49 Satisfactory Performance (SP)
- 2.50 – 3.49 Very Satisfactory Performance (VSP)
- 3.50 - 4.00 Excellent Performance (EP)

Table 4 presents the level of teaching competence of student teachers as observed by mentors across four domains: lesson planning, classroom management, instructional delivery, and assessment practices.

In terms of lesson planning, the highest weighted mean is “*aligned instructional objectives to the school’s pacing guide, program of studies*” with 3.43 (VSP), while the lowest mean is “*planned for differentiation*” with 3.26 (VSP). The composite mean of 3.34 (VSP) indicates that student teachers demonstrate very satisfactory performance in planning. This implies that while they are effective in aligning objectives and organizing instruction, differentiation remains a relatively less emphasized and more challenging aspect in addressing diverse learners’ needs.

For classroom management, the highest mean is “*established a climate of trust and teamwork...*” with 3.52 (EP), while the lowest mean is “*maximized instructional time and minimized disruptions*” with 3.42 (VSP). The composite mean of 3.46 (EP) shows that this domain has the highest performance among all areas. This suggests that student teachers excel in building positive classroom environments and relationships, although further improvement is needed in managing time efficiently and minimizing disruptions.

In terms of instructional delivery, the highest mean is “*engaged and maintains students in active learning*” with 3.47 (VSP), while the lowest mean is “*differentiated instruction to meet students’ needs*” with 3.30 (VSP). The composite mean of 3.41 (VSP) indicates very satisfactory performance. This implies that student teachers are effective in engaging learners and delivering content, but differentiation continues to be a consistent area needing enhancement.

For assessment practices, the highest mean is “*communicated expectations with clarity*” with 3.48 (VSP), while the lowest mean is “*gave constructive and frequent feedback*” with 3.40 (VSP). The composite mean of 3.45 (VSP) indicates very satisfactory performance. This suggests that while student teachers clearly communicate expectations and align assessments, providing consistent and meaningful feedback is slightly less emphasized.

Overall, the highest composite mean is found in classroom management (3.46, EP), while the lowest composite mean is in lesson planning (3.34, VSP). The overall composite mean of 3.42 (VSP) indicates that student teachers demonstrate very satisfactory teaching competence across all domains. This implies that they are generally well-prepared for professional teaching responsibilities, particularly in managing classroom environments, although continued development is needed in differentiation, lesson planning, and feedback practices. These findings are supported by recent studies. Adams et al. (2022) emphasized that effective classroom management is central to teaching success, particularly in fostering supportive learning environments. Similarly, Fukaya et al. (2024) highlighted the importance of strong lesson planning skills in preparing student teachers for actual classroom instruction. Furthermore, Sebulen (2023) noted that clear objectives and aligned assessments are essential for improving student learning outcomes.

Table 5
Differences Among Profile, Problems Encountered, Coping Strategies, and Teaching Competence
n=220

5.1 Between the Profile and the Problems Encountered					
Variable	χ^2	df	p	Interpretation	Decision
Age	24.60	36	.925	No significant difference	Failed to Reject H ₀
Gender	8.49	3	.037	Significant difference	Rejected H ₀
Course	13.20	9	.153	No significant difference	Failed to Reject H ₀
Smartphone	12.40	3	.006	Significant difference	Rejected H ₀
Laptop	0.99	3	.804	No significant difference	Failed to Reject H ₀
Tablet	0.08	3	.994	No significant difference	Failed to Reject H ₀
Audio-Visual	0.48	3	.924	No significant difference	Failed to Reject H ₀
PowerPoint	7.62	3	.054	No significant difference	Failed to Reject H ₀
Tarp Papel	7.98	3	.046	Significant difference	Rejected H ₀
5.2 Between the Profile and Coping Strategies					
Variable	χ^2	Df	p		Decision
Age	18.80	36	.992	No significant difference	Failed to Reject H ₀
Gender	0.79	3	.852	No significant difference	Failed to Reject H ₀
Course	5.11	9	.824	No significant difference	Failed to Reject H ₀
Smartphone	7.06	3	.070	No significant difference	Failed to Reject H ₀
Laptop	8.70	3	.033	Significant difference	Rejected H ₀
Tablet	11.20	3	.011	Significant difference	Rejected H ₀
Audio-Visual	1.82	3	.610	No significant difference	Failed to Reject H ₀

PowerPoint	7.62	3	.054	No significant difference	Failed to Reject H ₀
Tarp Papel	2.12	3	.549	No significant difference	Failed to Reject H ₀
5.3 Between the Profile and Teaching Competence					
Variable	χ²	df	p		Decision
Age	46.60	36	.110	No significant difference	Failed to Reject H ₀
Gender	3.99	3	.263	No significant difference	Failed to Reject H ₀
Course	14.00	9	.122	No significant difference	Failed to Reject H ₀
Smartphone	2.94	3	.401	No significant difference	Failed to Reject H ₀
Laptop	16.00	3	.001	Significant difference	Rejected H ₀
Tablet	3.57	3	.312	No significant difference	Failed to Reject H ₀
Audio-Visual	5.85	3	.119	No significant difference	Failed to Reject H ₀
PowerPoint	6.94	3	.074	No significant difference	Failed to Reject H ₀
Tarp Papel	7.66	3	.054	No significant difference	Failed to Reject H ₀

Table 5 presents the differences among profile variables, problems encountered, coping strategies, and teaching competence of student teachers as determined by the chi-square test.

For differences between profile and problems encountered (Table 5.1), most variables such as age ($p = .925$), course ($p = .153$), and the use of laptops ($p = .804$), tablets ($p = .994$), audio-visual materials ($p = .924$), and PowerPoint ($p = .054$) show no significant difference, leading to the decision to fail to reject the null hypothesis. This implies that these variables do not significantly influence the level of problems experienced by student teachers. However, gender ($p = .037$), smartphone use ($p = .006$), and tarpapel ($p = .046$) show significant differences, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. This indicates that gender and access to certain instructional materials contribute to variations in the problems encountered, suggesting that these factors may shape classroom experiences and challenges.

For differences between profile and coping strategies (Table 5.2), most variables including age ($p = .992$), gender ($p = .852$), course ($p = .824$), smartphone ($p = .070$), audio-visual materials ($p = .610$), PowerPoint ($p = .054$), and tarpapel ($p = .549$) show no significant difference, indicating that student teachers generally employ similar coping strategies regardless of these characteristics. In contrast, laptop ($p = .033$) and tablet ($p = .011$) show significant differences, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. This suggests that access to these technological tools influences how student teachers cope with challenges, particularly in handling academic and instructional demands.

For differences between profile and teaching competence (Table 5.3), almost all variables—age ($p = .110$), gender ($p = .263$), course ($p = .122$), smartphone ($p = .401$),

tablet ($p = .312$), audio-visual materials ($p = .119$), PowerPoint ($p = .074$), and tarpapel ($p = .054$)—show no significant difference, resulting in a failure to reject the null hypothesis. This indicates that teaching competence is generally consistent across these profile variables. Notably, laptop ($p = .001$) shows a significant difference, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. This implies that access to laptops plays a significant role in enhancing teaching competence, likely by supporting lesson preparation, instructional delivery, and assessment practices.

Overall, the findings reveal that most profile variables do not significantly influence the problems encountered, coping strategies, and teaching competence of student teachers. However, specific factors such as gender and access to technological resources (smartphones, laptops, tablets, and tarpapel) demonstrate significant effects in certain areas. This suggests that while student teachers generally share similar experiences and competencies, access to instructional tools and individual characteristics can shape particular outcomes. These findings are supported by recent studies. Tondeur et al. (2025) emphasized that access to digital tools significantly influences teaching practices and coping mechanisms among pre-service teachers. Similarly, Linda Darling-Hammond (2020) highlighted that teaching competence is largely shaped by training and professional preparation rather than demographic characteristics.

Table 6
Relationships Among Problems Encountered, Coping Strategies, and Teaching Competence

Variables Compared	Spearman's rho	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Problems Met vs. Coping Strategies	-0.311	< .001	Significant (Moderate Negative Relationship)	Reject H_0
Problems Met vs. Teaching Competence	-0.243	< .001	Significant (Weak Negative Relationship)	Reject H_0
Coping Strategies vs. Teaching Competence	0.591	< .001	Significant (Moderate Positive Relationship)	Reject H_0

Table 6 presents the Spearman rho correlation analysis showing the relationships among problems encountered, coping strategies, and teaching competence.

The findings reveal a moderate negative relationship between problems encountered and coping strategies ($\rho = -0.311$, $p < .001$). This indicates that as the level of problems increases, the use or effectiveness of coping strategies tends to decrease. This suggests that excessive challenges may overwhelm student teachers, making it more difficult for them to consistently apply effective coping mechanisms.

Similarly, there is a weak negative relationship between problems encountered and teaching competence ($\rho = -0.243$, $p < .001$). This implies that an increase in problems slightly reduces teaching performance, although the effect is not strong. This means that while student teachers can still perform despite challenges, higher levels of difficulties may hinder optimal teaching effectiveness.

On the other hand, the results show a moderate positive relationship between coping strategies and teaching competence ($\rho = 0.591, p < .001$). This indicates that student teachers who utilize stronger and more effective coping strategies tend to demonstrate higher levels of teaching competence. This highlights the critical role of coping mechanisms in sustaining performance despite challenges.

Overall, all relationships are statistically significant, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis in all cases. The pattern of relationships suggests that problems negatively influence both coping strategies and teaching competence, while coping strategies positively enhance teaching competence. The strongest relationship is observed between coping strategies and teaching competence, emphasizing that coping plays a more influential role in determining teaching performance compared to the direct effect of problems encountered. These findings are supported by recent studies. Castro (2021) highlighted the importance of supportive structures and professional development in enhancing performance outcomes. Similarly, Folkman and Lazarus (1988) emphasized that effective coping strategies buffer the negative effects of stress on performance outcomes.

DISCUSSION

This section presents the analysis of the status of secondary teaching internships, particularly in terms of the problems encountered, coping strategies, and teaching competence of student teachers. It also provides a description of the respondents' profile, including their age, gender, specialization/course, and the gadgets and instructional materials used in teaching. The discussion is organized according to the key variables of the study, including personal and academic problems, coping strategies for both areas, and teaching competence across lesson planning, classroom management, instructional delivery, and assessment practices, as well as the differences and relationships among these variables. The findings are interpreted using appropriate statistical measures.

Findings

The analysis of the statistical data revealed the following findings:

1. Profile of the Student Teachers

1.1 Age. The majority of the student teachers were between 20 and 23 years old, comprising 91.82 percent of the respondents.

1.2 Gender. Most of the student teachers were female, accounting for 73.18 percent.

1.3 Course. The majority of the student teachers were Bachelor of Secondary Education majors in English.

1.4 Gadgets and Instructional Materials Used. Laptops (26.43%) and PowerPoint (27.18%) were the most commonly used tools in teaching, with PowerPoint having the highest percentage among all instructional materials.

2. Level of Problems Met by the Student Teachers

2.1 Personal Aspect. The problems encountered by the student teachers had a composite mean of 1.85, interpreted as a minor concern.

2.2 Academic Knowledge. The academic aspect also yielded a mean of 1.63, indicating a minor concern.

3. Level of Coping Strategies Utilized by the Student Teachers. The coping strategies of the student teachers had an overall mean of 3.61, interpreted as a very high level. The personal aspect had a composite mean of 3.73, with the emotional aspect obtaining the highest mean of 3.32. Meanwhile, the academic aspect had a composite mean of 3.50, where both pedagogical and content domains recorded the highest composite mean of 3.38. These findings suggest that coping strategies are strongly practiced and may be influenced more by situational and resource-based factors than by personal characteristics.

4. Level of Teaching Competence of Student Teachers. The student teachers demonstrated very satisfactory teaching competence. Among the domains, classroom management had the highest composite mean of 3.46, indicating that student teachers were able to maintain an effective and organized learning environment.

5. Differences Among the Profiles and Problems Encountered, Coping Strategies, and Teaching Competence. The findings revealed that both demographic characteristics and access to specific learning tools are significantly associated with the problems encountered by student teachers. This suggests that individual differences and available resources shape their internship experiences. Moreover, technological accessibility, particularly the availability of laptops, plays a crucial role in supporting effective coping strategies. The absence of significant differences in other variables indicates that teaching competence is less influenced by demographic factors and more by access to and use of educational technologies. Overall, technology integration, especially the use of laptops, is a key factor in enhancing teaching competence.

6. Relationships Among the Level of Problems Encountered, Coping Strategies, and Teaching Competence. Coping strategies were found to be significantly related to both problems encountered and teaching competence, indicating their role in managing challenges and sustaining performance. Teaching competence was positively associated with the use of technological tools, particularly laptops, highlighting the importance of digital resources in instructional practice. Technology enhances lesson delivery by making it more engaging, flexible, and learner-centered, while also improving the efficiency of assessment.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, it is concluded that the problems encountered by student teachers have a negative influence on both their coping strategies and teaching competence, while coping strategies have a positive effect on teaching performance. Although challenges are present, these are generally at a low level, indicating that student teachers are organized and adequately prepared for their teaching internships. Furthermore, the high level of coping strategies demonstrates that student teachers are capable of effectively managing the demands of their internship. Emotional resilience, along with support from family, peers, mentors, and the school, plays a vital role in sustaining these coping mechanisms. Therefore, it is concluded that strong coping strategies significantly contribute to improved teaching competence, enabling student teachers to perform effectively despite the challenges encountered during their internship.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were crafted based on the major findings of the study.

1. The College Dean may consider designing stress management and financial literacy programs for student teachers to help them budget their allowances amid escalating commodity prices, and establishing academic support programs such as tutoring, mentoring, consultation hours, counselling, and stress management seminars.

2. The College President and Guidance Counselor may consider the possibility of budget allocation from the Board of Trustees for conducting seminars/workshops on financial literacy, a symposium on emotional resilience, socialization, and additional installation of equipment to ensure proper ventilation—a set of laptops and a projector intended for teaching simulation.

3. The school administrators and instructors may consider organizing a seminar training program focused on pedagogical skills and innovative teaching techniques. The schools and educational institutions should provide adequate access to technological resources, including laptops and tablets, conduct training programs focused on stress management and coping strategies, and improve the availability of instructional materials to reduce learning difficulties.

4. The course instructors handling professional subjects may strengthen their teaching techniques regarding lesson planning, classroom management, instructional delivery, and assessment practices. Instructors' competence can be developed through ongoing professional growth, including workshops, peer-to-peer mentoring, and reflective practice. Improving these competencies allows instructors to model appropriate teaching techniques that students can replicate in their own practice. The College President and instructors may consider the possibility of having the student teachers undergo seminar training as a simulation of the real world of teaching before deploying them to the cooperating schools.

5. Future researchers are encouraged to conduct similar studies with larger samples or different populations, explore additional variables such as emotional intelligence, motivation, and resilience, and utilize mixed-method approaches to gain deeper insights.

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE TEACH-HITC PROGRAM TRAINING FOR EFFECTIVE ADAPTIVE COPING AND HIGH TEACHING COMPETENCE

Rationale

The proposed action plan is designed to address the key findings of the study, particularly the roles of coping strategies and technology in improving teaching competence and reducing the problems encountered. The TEACH-HITC program comes from Training for Effective Adaptive Coping and High Teaching Competence. The plan emphasizes capacity-building activities such as training, workshops, and support systems to enhance student teachers' performance. In line with Republic Act No. 7784, Section 2, b) "An Act to Strengthen Teacher Education in the Philippines by Establishing Centers of Excellence, Creating a Teacher Education Council for the Purpose, Appropriating Funds Therefor, and for Other Purposes." Part of the teacher education curriculum consists of Teaching Internships, in which student teachers are placed in public secondary schools. This plan is intended to help local colleges and DepEd secondary schools maintain and improve technology integration and effective coping strategies, which are important factors associated with improved teaching competence among secondary student teachers, and to serve as a collaboration and extension program.

Furthermore, the integration of technology, especially laptops and tablets, is prioritized due to its significant influence on coping strategies and teaching competence. Continuous monitoring and evaluation are also included to ensure the effectiveness and sustainability of the proposed action plan.

General Objective

The TEACH-UP Program (Training for Effective Adaptive Coping and High Teaching Competence) aims to enhance student teachers' coping strategies, technological skills, and teaching competence by providing structured training, continuous support, and the effective integration of educational technologies throughout the internship period.

Specific Objectives

1. Reduced problems encountered by student teachers.
2. Enhanced students' coping strategies;
3. Improved teaching competence through technology integration;
4. Strengthened support systems in school; and
5. Monitored and evaluated implementation

Mechanism of Implementation of the TEACH-UP Program

The implementation of the TEACH-HiTC Program (Training for Effective Adaptive Coping and High Teaching) will follow a systematic and collaborative process to ensure the effective delivery of its activities and the attainment of its objectives.

Phase 1: Planning and Preparation

At the beginning of the academic year (June), school administrators, teachers, and guidance personnel will collaboratively plan the program. This includes identifying participants, preparing training materials, scheduling activities, and assigning responsibilities. Coordination with the ICT unit will also be conducted to ensure the availability of technological resources such as laptops and internet access.

Phase 2: Capacity Building and Training

During the first and second months (June–July), workshops and seminars on financial literacy, stress management, emotional resilience, pedagogical skills, and innovative teaching techniques will be held. Simultaneously, technology training sessions on the use of laptops, tablets, and educational applications will be provided. These activities aim to equip student teachers with the necessary skills to handle personal and academic challenges and to improve their teaching competence through technology integration.

Phase 3: Program Implementation

From July to April, the program's core activities will be implemented. Student teachers will participate in continuous development programs and seminars, integrate technology into their teaching practices, and engage in academic support systems such as mentoring, tutoring, and peer collaboration. Guidance services and peer support groups will also be made available to address emotional and academic concerns.

Phase 4: Monitoring and Evaluation

Monitoring and evaluation will be conducted periodically (in August, October, January, March, and May) to assess the program's progress and effectiveness. Surveys, feedback forms, and performance assessments will be utilized to gather data. The results will be used to identify areas for improvement and ensure that the program remains responsive to the needs of the student teachers.

Phase 5: Feedback and Continuous Improvement

Based on the evaluation results, necessary adjustments will be made to improve the program's implementation.

Schedule of Implementation

The program implementation relies on and is based on the approval and recommendation of the college president.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study adhered to recognized ethical standards for educational research. Participation was voluntary, and informed consent was obtained from all respondents after explaining the study's purpose, procedures, and their rights. Respondents were free to withdraw at any time without penalty.

Confidentiality and anonymity were strictly maintained, with no personally identifiable information collected. All data were securely stored and used solely for academic purposes in compliance with the Philippine Data Privacy Act of 2012 (Republic Act No. 10173). The study posed no risk to participants, and no conflict of interest or financial incentives were involved.

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